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HISTORY OF PILGRIM TOURISM AND ITS CONTENTS IN THE FIELD OF TOURISMLPLACE

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***Abstract:** The results of the research show that the development of pilgrimage tourism is one of the directions of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. Its important features and opportunities for increasing employment, income and wellbeing of the population are shown by the authors in this article.*

***Key words:** tourism, economics, pilgrimage, tourist, religion, monument, grave, employment, population, income, abundance, induction, deduction, systematics, analysis, trend and others.*

Pilgrimage tourism is a set of pilgrimage trips by representatives of different religions. Traditionally, it refers to trips with a religious purpose, but it can also refer to a secular trip that has special significance for the pilgrim. Pilgrimage tourism importance two to the feature according to justification can: pilgrimage tourism how much for the shrine is important. A pilgrimage for pilgrims How important is tourism? Pilgrimage is spiritual nourishment for many people in difficult times get opportunity is also People religious enlightenment feeling to do for known to addresses travel they do Most of the time long and sometimes difficult has been travel people for thought conduct is a possibility. Pilgrimages religion with relationships of deepening one method to be possible this, of course, to faith How a way to show devotion and learn more about the religion itself is a possibility. Pilgrimage as a form of travel is for people to visit holy places to do opportunity will give. Religious purposes travel doer traveler - no more than six months to visit holy places and religious centers means a person who temporarily leaves the country of permanent residence. Religious tourism means usual from the environment was outside holy places and service to travelers traveling to religious centers show and their by meeting their needs related activities must be understood.

BOOKS ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Religious tourism two main ones type divided into:

- pilgrimage tourism;
- excursion and educational direction religious tourism

Today, more than 200 million people around the world make pilgrimages every year in order to in the world different shrines and themselves for holy calculated going to places and making religious trips. Statistical data if we look at it, 150 million Christians, 45 million Muslims, 40 million Buddhists and shinto, 30 million Hindus religious pilgrimage in order to travel they do.

Religious pilgrimage has been a unique mass in the form of the Crusades since the Middle Ages acquired a character. SHE IS flag of struggle against Muslims under, of Christians holy places of them free to do motto under conducted.

Pilgrimage actions XV – XVI in centuries much activated. holy land to (Jerusalem). those who are going most of them own goals and interests religious pilgrimage with disguised.

Shrines wide and different geography learning for from zoning is used. In the world visit one how much macro area there is:

- Christian Europe; Christianity and another many people religions with strong place occupying North America;
- Christianity and traditional religions with connected Latin America;
- Islam acceptance did North Africa;
- Islam dominant and separately Christianity and traditional religions there is Western and Eastern Africa;
- Islam ,buddhism, Christianity and i am hindu religions wide spread out Eastern Asia;
- Islam religion wide spread out Medium Asia;
- Western Asia - islam and christianity, Judaism religions wide spread out territory;
- South Asia Judaism and Buddhism wide spread out area is consideredAlso Christianity, jainism, Sikhism and islam religions there is.

Each macro-region is known primarily for its world centers of pilgrimage. They are of believers international flow acceptance, they do and often religious functions of administrative, industrial, cultural and touristic centers of specialization with joined goes From this except in macro areas national and local there are important religious objects of worship. Jerusalem is the largest city in the world is one of the religious centers. Believers of three religions in Jerusalem: Islam, Christianity, Judaism for holy is also the center.

These macro-regions arose from the potential of existing religious shrines without separated. They are inside the most important region in Europe vatican, Western In Asia, Mecca and Medina in Saudi Arabia and the cities of Jerusalem are considered. In Central Asia, Uzbekistan's ancient Bukhara and Samarkand, Tashkent, Termiz, Khiva and other religious in cities touristic resources there is.

Pilgrimages are usually to the shrines of famous figures of different religions visit to order reflection makes A visit ordered place holy that it was Because many people pray here, it is more likely that the prayer will be answered that means Some shrines and places their own income for Entirely of tourism this impressive to the power rely on. this, own in turn, around to regions too own the effect conducts. Tourists hotel and restaurants for rent takes Guides, in hand souvenir gifts makers photographers and work for others seats is created.

However, according to the famous scientist Vukonich, the economic of religious travel aspects religion - tourism to the term relatively the most less studied topic being of interest to researchers when only one sanctuary is considered. Religious pilgrimage pilgrims visit commanding in the regions economic generator task done came because services their needs satisfy for work developed. This today's even in the day the same so.

Because a lot in places religious places main touristic attention deserves places being sometimes Santiago de Compostela, Medjugorje, Lourdes and Mecca such as into himself takes

Indeed, tourism is not only economic development and gross domestic product of size increase, perhaps population employment provide marriage level and quality increase, country prosperity and development also a big influence shows. According to experts' calculations, every 30 tourists are tourists of the country incentive to create one new job in the field, and two new jobs in related systems will give. Many countries and population points tourism difficult in the situation has been seen as a way to revive or save the economy, especially the current tourism forecasts, as mentioned above, that religious tourism will increase in the near future shows.

in Uzbekistan pilgrimage tourism.

About pilgrimage tourism, Uzbek Islamic scholar BMBobojonov, Central The most common type of pilgrimage site in Asia is "holy shrines". to be considered telling passed. Surkhandarya regions historical objects a scientist who studies architecture from the point of view of architecture In the study of I. Azimov to the eye thrown away. Sufism representatives steps and shrines about A. Mamanazarov, B. Sattarov, Poslavskaya. O, S. Jorayeva too pilgrimage tourism to history around stopping passed. Uzbekistan in the area shrines the issue in learning shrine name with dependent person personification Researching the status and level of (saint, pir, said, khoja) is also

considered important. T. Dadabayev, E. Karimov in his studies too pilgrimage of the issue different aspects on the surface feedback given. Including D. Abramson and E. Karimov in the article co-authored, visit in the life of the peoples of Central Asia importance, different in periods to him was relationship analysis will be done.

And this is not just a trip, this is an opportunity to realize yourself, spiritually hope for purification, praying for the fulfillment of prayers and wishes, the path leading to faith. Pilgrimage isturning to the Almighty God through past saints, calming the mind and soul, realizing the truth of holiness, going through the path of solitude and purification. Central in Asia this Pilgrimage that called this holy to places visit to order means Uzbekistan each always many cultures and of civilizations It has been a center of intersection, where different religions have been propagated, that's why unique monuments of both Islam, Buddhism and Christianity are preserved the rest Indeed, Uzbekistan is rich in tourist resources separate stands in Uzbekistan religious tourism, i.e dear There are enough places to visit the shrines. In particular, in Central Asia, moreover in Uzbekistan too dear the saints living funeral done steps, pilgrimage residences a lot

Many of the saints funeral done places and graves again repaired original to the situation is being brought. They are to the line Bahaviddin embroidery, Gijduvani, Imam al-Bukhari, Meaning Member, in Shahizin, Motirudi, Judge at-Tirmidhi, The mausoleums of saints and imams like Zangiota are incomparable for Muslim people, it was turned into a beautiful place of pilgrimage and spiritual inspiration. Especially, Turning the Imam Al-Bukhari complex into an important pilgrimage site is of international importance has Because this pilgrimage is from the cities of Mecca and Medina in the Muslim world then it is the most important place of worship. Therefore, a favorable condition for visiting -creating conditions, i.e. forming infrastructure, is an important issue today is calculated. This on the ground main task abroad countries citizens excess without difficulties to visit is what we can achieve.

Independence years religious to the steps state by big attention is being given. Great our ancestors my soul found residences again recovery, beautification, to repair serious attention that he gave because of shrine places It attracts the 1.5 billion Muslim world. Pilgrimage tourism today development main the goal by doing received we are first of all in our country religious tourism territorial organize reach and to develop serious attention focus must In particular, the countries of South-East Asia and West Asia attract pilgrims we need to develop attractive infrastructures. For this purpose one region, district and in villages people by holy considered Identifying, summarizing, republican and regional religious shrines creating tourist cards and creating necessary conditions for visitors, transport opportunities learning is the goal as appropriate we count.

Turning religious shrines into a large source of income at the expense of small funds no doubt. Dozens and hundreds of religious shrines from all regions of our country there is. Islam in the world big service do saint level raised the eternal abodes of our figures are only at the local level, i.e district or region scale we know only Consequently, such holy shrines republic and international level religious shrine objects can be converted. At the same time, to major pilgrimage sites in the territory of the republic establishment of a road transport system in the region population another to the area organized travel for them to do transport commutes to the road pouring provided. From this except in our country is located islam culture and cultural heritage objects related to the history of the Islamic cultural organization of the Islamic Cooperation Organization legacy to the list implementation measures is increased.

Widespread development of internal and external tourism, tourism industry in the republic modernization, the field stable develop, tourism centers calculated in the regions tourist, household and communication-information infrastructures develop, local and foreign to the guests international to standards according to services to show separately attention focus important importance occupation It is enough. Emphasis ok this about defined events done increase, in our country tourism field development the first in line the world in the community of Uzbekistan position strengthens, new opportunities for foreign investors and reliable cooperation the doors opens country macroeconomic indicators stability, population a factor in the improvement of indicators such as income, employment and entrepreneurship being services of the field again improvement reason will be.

CONCLUSIONS

Current in the day fast in pictures becoming popular going tourism field The development of pilgrimage tourism has a high potential in this area countries for comfortable is a possibility. Above cause passed from thoughts and from the examples it can be concluded that every member of the country is that including foreign countries should follow sustainable pilgrimage tourism It is necessary to develop important policies and strategies for development. From this except foreign tourists attraction do it will receive infrastructure Create important importance occupation is enough. In order to implement sustainable development, the government, too local should be coordinated by the agencies.

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